

GENDER BARRIERS FACED BY WOMEN CHEFS' IN PROFESSIONAL KITCHEN

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to determine the gender barriers faced by female chefs working in the kitchen departments of five-star hotels in Antalya, the factors that prevent them from progressing in their careers, and the situations they have to struggle with. In addition, it is aimed to determine the perception of gender in hotel kitchens based on the experiences of successful and well-known female chefs in professional kitchens. In the quantitative part of the study it has been determined that there is no significant difference between the difficulties encountered in the business life of the female cooks participating in the research and the situations they have to struggle with and the demographic variables. In the qualitative part of the study it has been determined that female cooks working in the kitchen unit face many difficulties, both physical and psychological, such as sexual harassment, slang and mobbing. As a result, the statements made by female chefs in the study show that gender barriers continue in professional kitchens today. While working in the kitchen department, many difficulties are encountered, both physical and psychological. Regardless of their gender, women working in professional kitchens should be treated equally and fairly in the distribution and distribution of duties within the sector.

Keywords: Female Chefs; Kitchen; Gastronomy.

BARREIRAS DE GÉNERO ENFRENTADAS POR CHEFS FEMININOS NA COZINHA PROFISSIONAL**Resumo**

O objetivo deste estudo é determinar as barreiras de gênero enfrentadas pelas chefs que trabalham nos departamentos de cozinha de hotéis de cinco estrelas em Antália, os fatores que os impedem de progredir nas suas carreiras, e as situações com que têm de lutar. Além disso, destina-se a determinar a percepção do gênero nas cozinhas do hotel com base nas experiências de chefs femininos bem-sucedidos e bem conhecidos em cozinhas profissionais. Na parte quântica do estudo determinou-se que não há uma diferença significativa entre as dificuldades encontradas na vida empresarial das cozinheiras femininas que participam na investigação e as situações com que têm de lutar e as variáveis demográficas. Na parte qualitativa do estudo foi determinado que as cozinheiras femininas que trabalham na unidade de cozinha enfrentam muitas dificuldades, tanto físicas como psicológicas, como assédio sexual, gíria e mobbing. Como resultado, as declarações feitas pelas chefs mulheres no estudo mostram que as barreiras de gênero continuam hoje nas cozinhas profissionais. Ao trabalhar na cozinha, muitas dificuldades são encontradas, tanto físicas quanto psicológicas. Ao trabalhar na cozinha, muitas dificuldades são encontradas, tanto físicas quanto psicológicas. Independentemente do gênero, as mulheres que trabalham em cozinhas profissionais devem ser tratadas de forma igual e justa na distribuição e distribuição de funções dentro do setor.

Palavras-chave: Chefs Femininos; Culinária; Gastronomia.

BARRERAS DE GÉNERO QUE ENFRENTAN LAS MUJERES CHEFS EN LA COCINA PROFESIONAL**Resumen**

El objetivo de este estudio es determinar las barreras de género a las que se enfrentan las chefs que trabajan en los departamentos de cocina de los hoteles de cinco estrellas en Antalya, los factores que les impiden progresar en sus carreras y las situaciones con las que tienen que luchar. Además, tiene como objetivo determinar la percepción de género en las cocinas de los hoteles a partir de las experiencias de chefs exitosas y conocidas en cocinas profesionales. En la parte cuantitativa del estudio se ha determinado que no existe una diferencia significativa entre las dificultades encontradas en la vida empresarial de las cocineras que participan en la investigación y las situaciones con las que tienen que luchar y las variables demográficas. En la parte cualitativa del estudio se ha determinado que las cocineras que trabajan en la unidad de cocina se enfrentan a muchas dificultades, tanto físicas como psicológicas, como el acoso sexual, el argot y el mobbing. Como resultado, las declaraciones de las cocineras en el estudio muestran que las barreras de género continúan hoy en las cocinas profesionales. Mientras se trabaja en el departamento de cocina, se enfrentan muchas dificultades, tanto físicas como psicológicas. Mientras se trabaja en el departamento de cocina, se enfrentan muchas dificultades, tanto físicas como psicológicas. Independentemente de su género, las mujeres que trabajan en cocinas profesionales deben recibir un trato equitativo y justo en el reparto y reparto de funciones dentro del sector.

Palabras clave: Mujeres Chefs; Culinária; Gastronomía.

1 INTRODUCTION

Gender, which emphasizes the roles of femininity and masculinity, is a concept that challenges the cultural structure in order to change these roles attributed by society (İşman and Yusupova, 2023:63). Gender, which expresses the process that begins with the birth of individuals, includes the structural, functional and behavioral characteristics determined by the sex chromosomes of living things (Akkaş, 2019:97; Torgrimson and Minson, 2005:885).

Gender discrimination arises from the belief that one gender is superior to the other (Klutsey, 2020: 25). Gender roles contribute to the formation and development of gender discrimination (Cejka and Eagly, 1999: 413). The duties that women are expected to perform due to their social roles affect their social hierarchies, creating gender discrimination (Zeeshan, 2020: 4).

The society always has ideas about how women's behavior should be. In social life, individuals are divided into two according to their sexual differences in the social norms

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and values system. The fact that individuals face such a classification creates gender discrimination (D'Amico and Nardocci 2021: 84). Gender discrimination, which dates back to ancient times, still affects many women around the world and exposes them to many injustices in their workplace and social life (Childs, 2011: 2).

Dominant gender stereotypes still shape men's and women's choices regarding preferred fields of work today. (Romero, Cruz and Romero, 2021: 303; Costa, Carvalho, Caçador and Breda, 2012: 72). As women and men are treated differently in the workplace, women face many gender barriers in developing their career identities (Yang, 2010: 120). Although incentives are increased in organizations and social life with various policies and sanctions for gender equality, it is clearly seen that there is inequality between women and men in economic equality criteria (Trentham and Larwood, 1998: 1).

Most of the organizations that make up the hotel industry employ a large number of women. However, there is a decrease in the ratio of women in middle and senior management positions (Qu, Jo and Choi, 2019: 78). Today, many restaurant operators or head chefs are men; they keep women away from the cooking they perform in their own kitchens (Platzer, 2011: 3). Therefore, women in the culinary sector can reach their current position by going through long and difficult processes (FungaiZengeni, Tendani and Zengeni, 2014: 3). 1).

In line with this information, the aim of the research is to determine the gender barriers faced by female chefs working in the kitchen departments of 5-star hotels in Antalya, the factors that prevent them from progressing in their careers, and the situations they have to struggle with. In addition, it is aimed to determine the gender perception in hotel kitchens, the effect of gender perceptions on performance and whether gender discrimination has an effect as a motivation in their struggle with the difficulties they encounter in the kitchen, based on the experiences of successful and well-known female chefs in professional kitchens.

In this study, the difficulties faced by female chefs in the kitchen and the reasons that prevent them from

advancing in their careers were determined and suggestions were tried to be made. Although gender discrimination is not the only obstacle to the advancement of women in their culinary careers, it can be caused by many factors. At this point, it is important to identify these barriers so that female chefs can have more space in the sector.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Gender Barriers Faced by Women in Hotel Kitchens

Although the food and beverage industry is seen as a male-dominated line of business, just like engineering or medicine, it is traditionally thought to be an area dominated by women. In terms of gender roles, cooking and putting hot meals on the table is a duty that women must fulfill. Some researchers even claim that cooking has a biological role for women (Platzer, 2011: 2).

While women primarily work in contract work, they are often limited to gender-based roles such as childcare, cooking, and cleaning (Markose, Bindu, Brown and George, 2023:2). However, today, the fame of the art of cooking and the idea that it provides a status to the person has been an indication that this paradigm and gender discrimination has begun to break (Madichie, 2013: 90-91). The kitchen has always been a place where women feel free and see it as an area of dominance. However, over time, creating a plate of food has turned into an area including men (Aarseth and Olsen, 2008: 278).

Although there is no doubt about the talent, skill and creativity of women in the kitchen, the idea that women have a place in the home kitchen and that the man is in the professional kitchen has continued (Druckman, 2010: 24). Women who had difficulty in finding a job in the kitchen in the 17th century, when it was not as common for women to work outside as it is today, realized that they had the ability to work in the kitchen, when a female chef named MartheDistell started to teach cooking classes at Le CordonBleu (FungaiZengeni, Tendani and Zengeni, 2014: 4).

Table 1. Related Studies on Gender Discrimination and Gender Barriers.

Abassah-Oppong and Holmes (2020)	Abassah-Oppong and Holmes (2020) aimed to determine the gender imbalance in the senior administrative structure of hotels in Calgary, Canada, and to determine the factors that affect this imbalance. In the study, data was obtained by conducting a survey to the management teams of nine hotels. It was revealed as a result of the research organizational barriers were the most dominant factor restricting the job descriptions of all hotel employees, regardless of gender.
Bijsterveldt (2020)	Bijsterveldt (2020) tried to reveal to what extent women working in the hospitality industry can reach senior management positions, to identify the different obstacles that must be overcome to reach such a position, and how these obstacles can be overcome. The data in the study was obtained by interviewing women working in the hotel sector. According to these data, it is stated that gender inequality and glass ceiling syndrome against women continue in the hospitality industry.
Garrigos, Haddaji, Segovia, and Signes (2019)	Garrigos, et al. (2019) aimed to determine the development of chefs' careers in general and whether there are any obstacles to the advancement of women in working life. As a result of the data obtained from the study, it was determined that female chefs had difficulty in establishing work-life balance, put aside the idea of starting a family, and had to give up their personal lives.
Min (2019)	Min (2019) aimed to examine the data collected from some media sources and publications by comparing the representation percentages of male and female cooks working in various fields in professional kitchens. As a result of the study, it was determined that the media reinforced the difficulties that female chefs had to endure and caused them to be seen as a normal situation. It has also been revealed that the masculine structure that prevails in professional kitchens affects women's career choices and that female employees are reluctant to work in the kitchen department.
Cano (2019)	Cano (2019) aimed to determine the gender perceptions of individuals working in professional kitchens in the El Paso region and to understand and research the main problems of gender inequality in kitchen departments. Data in the study were obtained through interviews with 12 male and 12 female chefs working in the culinary industry. As a result of the study, it was revealed that the majority of cooks were women, an important symbol for the kitchen, but they were the second choice in recruitment in professional kitchens and started working at low levels. In addition, the idea that male cooks working in professional kitchens are more determined and professional than women puts men in a privileged position.

Source: own elaboration.

Women who were late in obtaining employment in the kitchen found less place in hotel kitchens than men who held high positions as head chef or section chef in industry reports (Harris and Giuffre, 2010: 31). Considering the gender ratios of individuals working in professional kitchens, it is seen that women are less involved than men. (Arnoldsson, 2015: 7). The biggest reason for this can be expressed as the fact that male chefs attract more attention from the society and the difficulties that female chefs face in terms of recognition and acceptance in the sector continue. (Agmapişan, 2016: 24).

There are traces of gender roles and prejudices rather than assertiveness or competence in the advancement of women in their career journey (Winn, 2004: 144). In professional kitchens dominated by men, although women compete at the same level in many areas, including long working hours, they are exposed to the unequal distribution of family responsibilities (Haddaji, Garrigós, and Segovia, 2017: 322).

The structural organization and masculine atmosphere of the professional kitchen, due to the role that the society they live in has assigned to women, and the fact that their physical stamina is insufficient for the kitchen have led them to have no representation in the kitchen and to different career paths related to the kitchen (Platzer, 2011: 6).

Another problem for women working in the sector arises from the perspectives of their families and society. Many women working in the sector do not receive sufficient support from their families and have difficulty establishing work-life balance (Vizcaino- Suárez, Serrano Barquín, Cruz Jiménez and Pastor Alfonso, 2017: 393).

In such cases, women remain under the pressure of being between their own psychology and social roles as well as external factors and this prevents women's employment in tourism (Li and Leung, 2001: 192). Uncertainty of working hours and shift work system in tourism are the most important reasons for women's inability to maintain work-life balance and the occurrence of double liability (Dumbrăveanu, Light, Young, and Chapman, 2016: 165).

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The use of mixed methods produces sharper and more complete information on theory and practice. It reveals different views that may be overlooked in a study using a single method (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004: 21). Mixed research method was applied in the research and data was collected both qualitatively and quantitatively.

3.1 The Purpose and Importance of the Research

In this study, it is aimed to determine the gender barriers that female chefs working in the kitchen departments of 5-star hotels in Antalya encounter in their business life, the factors that prevent them from progressing in their careers, and the situations they have to struggle with. In addition, based on the experiences of professionally successful female chefs in kitchens, the effect of gender on interaction with colleagues, subordinates and superiors, the effect of gender perceptions on performance and the degree of difficulties they encounter in the kitchen have been tried to be revealed.

3.2 Research Hypotheses

The main problem of the research is to determine the gender barriers faced by female chefs working in the kitchen unit of five-star hotels in Antalya, the factors that prevent them from progressing in their careers, and the situations they have to struggle with. Based on this information, the following hypotheses have been developed (Li and Leung, 2001; Ng and Pine, 2003; Kinias and Kim, 2011; Garrigós, Haddaji, Segovia and Signes, 2019; Remington and Kitterlin, 2018):

H1: There is a significant difference between the sub-dimensions of gender barriers according to the socio-demographic characteristics of female cooks.

H1a: There is a significant difference between the age groups of female cooks and the lack of support resources.

H1b: There is a significant difference between the marital status of female cooks and the lack of support resources.

H1c: There is a significant difference between the education levels of female cooks and the lack of support resources.

H1d: There is a significant difference between the income levels of female cooks and the lack of support resources.

H1e: There is a significant difference between the age groups of female cooks and the lack of mentors.

H1f: There is a significant difference between the marital status of female cooks and the lack of mentors.

H1g: There is a significant difference between the education levels of female cooks and the lack of mentors.

H1h: There is a significant difference between the income levels of female cooks and the lack of mentors.

H1i: There is a significant difference between the age groups of female cooks and gender discrimination.

H1j: There is a significant difference between the marital status of female cooks and gender discrimination.

H1k: There is a significant difference between the education levels of female cooks and gender discrimination.

H1l: There is a significant difference between the income levels of female cooks and gender discrimination.

H1m: There is a significant difference between age groups of female cooks and organizational conditions.

H1n: There is a significant difference between the marital status of female cooks and organizational conditions.

H1o: There is a significant difference between the educational status of female cooks and organizational conditions.

H1p: There is a significant difference between the income levels of female cooks and organizational conditions.

3.3 Research Population and Sample

The population of the research consists of female cooks working in the kitchen departments of 5-star hotels in Antalya. According to the "Tourism Operation Certified Facility" list updated by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism on 02.12.2019, it was determined that there are 324 five-star hotels in Antalya. In order to calculate the number of samples, the formula of Özdamar (2003: 116-118) in limited universe situations was used. In line with the calculation, it is

sufficient to include at least 321 of the female chefs working in five-star hotels in Antalya.

The limitations of the research are given below;

The research will be limited to Antalya province. The reason why Antalya was chosen is that it is seen as a large market in the tourism sector.

Due to time and money constraints, the research was limited to only female cooks working in five-star hotels.

Since city hotels are busy every season, meeting with female chefs and the difficulty of filling out the survey constitute another limitation.

3.4 Data Collection Method and Analysis

3.4.1 Quantitative Data Collection Method

In the study, the questionnaire questions used by Yilmaz (2018) in his doctoral thesis were developed in accordance with the purpose of the research and the necessary permissions were obtained from the author. The first part of the questionnaire includes demographic questions. In the second part, there are various expressions about the obstacles faced by female cooks and the process of ending the behaviors they develop when faced with these obstacles.

The survey application was carried out with female chefs working in the kitchen departments of five-star hotels in Antalya. In order to reach the sample number, a support application was made in order to meet the survey service within the scope of Necmettin Erbakan University Scientific Research Projects (BAP). After the acceptance of the application, within the scope of the budget support determined for the research, a survey service was received from the survey company in order to determine the opinions of the female chefs working in the kitchen departments of the five-star hotels in Antalya.

The filling process of the surveys undertaken by the survey company took place between 02.01.2020 and 08.04.2020. After the application of the questionnaires, a total of 330 questionnaire forms were considered valid and analyzed within the scope of the research by checking whether the questions were filled in completely. In the research, data were analyzed through a statistical analysis program. First of all, accuracy checks were made and frequency distributions, averages and standard deviations were examined. The next step was outlier research. After the data was prepared for the analysis process, factor analysis, t-test and ANOVA analysis were used.

3.4.2 Qualitative Data Collection Method

In the study, the interview questions used by Cano (2019) in his master's thesis were arranged in accordance with the research purpose. Interview questions were directed to 32 successful female chefs in professional kitchens. In the first part of the interview form, demographic questions were included, while in the second part, it was aimed to determine the gender barriers they encountered and their perceptions of gender barriers based on their professional kitchen experiences. Due to the pandemic process, the interview

was held between January and April 2021 with the resource persons via online, e-mail and phone calls. The interview forms were filled in personally by the female chefs and sent to the researcher via e-mail.

4 FINDINGS

4.1 Quantitative Research Findings

4.1.1 Findings Regarding the Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Of the 330 female participants participating in the research; It is seen that 48.2% of them are in the 25-34 age range, 27.6% are in the 18-24 age range, and 24.2% are in the 35 and over age range. Participants; 58.8% are single, 41.2% are married. As the years of working in the profession of the participants; 36.4% between 4-6 years, 27.3% between 7-9 years, 22.1% between 10-12 years, 8.3% between 1-3 years, 5% It is seen that 0.8 of them are 13 years and over.

Considering the position of the participants in the kitchen; 57.6% of them are busboys, 17.9% are Demi Chef, 7.3% are Patisserie Chefs, 6.7% are Cold Chefs, 3.6% are Hot Chefs, 2.7% are It was determined that 2.4% worked as A la Carte Chef, 0.6% as Assistant Chef, 0.3% as Banquet Chef, 0.6% as Butcher Chef and 0.3% as Head Chef. 70.9% of the participants are permanently employed and 29.1% are contracted. It was determined that 52.1% of the participants worked between 8 or 9 hours during the day, while 47.9% of them worked 10 hours or more.

It was determined that 40.6% of female chefs working in five-star hotels in Antalya received tourism training and 59.7% received culinary training. It was determined that 43.1% of the 197 participants who received culinary training received training from public education centers, 28.9% from universities and 27.9% from private culinary courses.

4.1.2 Findings Related to Factor Analysis

Explanatory factor analysis of the scale of the difficulties encountered in business life and the situations that had to be struggled was made.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) criterion is an important adequacy criterion in evaluating the scale's suitability for factor analysis. KMO takes a value between 0-1 and if the value is less than 0.5, the data is not considered suitable for analysis (Cerny and Kaiser, 1977: 43-47). In this study, the KMO criterion was examined for factor analysis. The KMO value was found to be 0.657. If the KMO value is between 0.5 and 0.7, it means that the value is at the acceptable cut-off point. In this context, it was concluded that factor analysis could be performed on the data. As a result of the analysis, it was determined that there were a total of four factors with eigenvalues above 1. The contribution rate of these factors to the total variance is 57.099%. The analysis results are shown in table 2.

Table 2. Factor Analysis Results Regarding the Scale of Difficulties Encountered in Business Life and Situations Enforced to Struggle.

		Expressions	Factor Load	Homogeneity	Eigenvalue	Explained Variance (%)
Lack of Support Resources	3.5	I have faced social exclusion at many stages of my career.	0,808	0,688	2,401	21,825
	3.4	Until I reached this stage, I had difficulties in catching career development opportunities.	0,646	0,505		
	3.6	I did not receive support from my managers until I reached this stage.	0,583	0,644		
Lack of Mentor	3.2	I didn't have a role model that helped shape my career.	0,773	0,629	1,577	14,333
	3.1	I encountered the situation of not being able to enter the network networks in the area where I work.	0,740	0,632		
	3.3	I don't think my hard work is rewarded.	0,480	0,329		
Gender Discrimination	3.9	I have lived with the existence of macho culture (male-dominated organizational culture) in many stages.	0,818	0,695	1,273	11,572
	3.10	I was unable to take advantage of the learning opportunities at many stages.	0,666	0,502		
	3.11	I faced gender discrimination at many stages.	0,384	0,502		
Organizational Conditions	3.7	At many stages I was paid less than men.	0,799	0,665	1,031	9,369
	3.8	Until I reached this stage, I was prevented from being promoted due to discrimination based on my gender.	0,505	0,567		

Source: own elaboration.

4.1.3 Findings Related to Research Hypotheses

In order to compare the sub-dimensions of 'deprivation of support resources', 'lack of mentors', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' of the scale of

difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to struggle, according to socio-demographic characteristics, t-test for independent samples in bivariate groups (Independent samples t-test); ANOVA analysis was performed in groups with more than two variables.

Table 3. ANOVA analysis of the sub-dimensions of 'lack of sources of support', 'lack of mentors', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' of the scale of difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to be struggled according to the participants' age groups.

Dimensions	Age group	n	X	s.s.	F value	P value	
Scale of difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to be struggled	Lack of Support Resources	18-24	91	3,5238	0,6854	0,662	0,517
		25-34	159	3,6184	0,04813		
		35 and older	80	3,5667	0,67380		
	Lack of Mentor	18-24	91	3,4469	0,64830	1,827	0,162
		25-34	159	3,6122	0,65160		
		35 and older	80	3,5083	0,77036		
	Gender Discrimination	18-24	91	3,6923	0,54258	0,842	0,432
		25-34	159	3,7610	0,53319		
		35 and older	80	3,6792	0,49879		
Organizational Conditions	18-24	91	3,5330	0,66166	0,915	0,402	
	25-34	159	3,6509	0,68611			
	35 and older	80	3,5688	0,77027			

Source: Elaborated with research data (2021).

It is observed that there is no significant difference between the scores of the participants in the sub-dimensions of 'lack of support resources', 'lack of mentors', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' and age variables of the scale of difficulties encountered in business life and the situations they have to struggle with (Sig.= 0.517, Sig.=0.162, Sig.=0.432, and Sig.=0.402). Consequently;

H1a: 'There is a significant difference between the age

groups of female cooks and the lack of support resources.'

H1e: 'There is a significant difference between the age groups of female cooks and the lack of mentors.'

H1i: 'There is a significant difference between the age groups of female cooks and gender discrimination.'

H1l: 'There is a significant difference between the age groups of female cooks and organizational conditions.' hypothesis was rejected.'

Table 4. The t-test results of the sub-dimensions of 'lack of sources of support', 'lack of mentors', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' of the scale of difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to struggle according to the participants' marital status.

Dimensions	Marital status	n	X	s.s.	t value	p value	
Scale of difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to be struggled	Lack of Support Resources	Married	194	3,5945	0,61215	0,142	0,617
		Single	136	3,5588	0,67022		
	Lack of Mentor	Married	194	3,5258	0,65329	0,501	0,620
		Single	136	3,5637	0,72522		
	Gender Discrimination	Married	194	3,7337	0,56534	-0,496	0,638
		Single	136	3,7059	0,46976		
	Organizational Conditions	Married	194	3,6031	0,67116	0,471	0,887
		Single	136	3,5919	0,74337		

Source: own elaboration.

It is observed that there is no significant difference between the scores of the participants in the sub-dimensions of 'lack of support resources', 'lack of mentors', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' and the marital status variable of the scale of difficulties encountered in business life and the situations they have to struggle with (Sig. =0.617, Sig.=0.620, Sig.=0.638, and Sig.=0.887. Consequently;

H1b: 'There is a significant difference between the

marital status of female cooks and the lack of support resources.'

H1f: 'There is a significant difference between the marital status of female cooks and the lack of mentors.'

H1i: 'There is a significant difference between the marital status of female cooks and gender discrimination.'

H1m: 'There is a significant difference between the marital status of female cooks and organizational conditions.' hypothesis was rejected.

Table 5. ANOVA test results of the sub-dimensions of 'lack of sources of support', 'lack of mentors', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' of the scale of difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to struggle according to the participants' education level.

	Dimension	Educational Status	n	X	s.s.	F value	p value
Scale of difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to be struggled	Lack of Support Resources	Primary school	-	-	-	2,155	0,093
		Middle School	61	3,6831	0,62783		
		High school	199	3,5360	0,62110		
		Associate Degree	39	3,7436	0,71107		
		Bachelor's	31	3,4516	0,61191		
		Postgraduate	-	-	-		
	Lack of Mentor	Primary school	-	-	-	0,318	0,813
		Middle School	61	3,5246	0,74152		
		High school	199	3,5243	0,64558		
		Associate Degree	39	3,5726	0,74907		
		Bachelor's	31	3,6452	0,73503		
		Postgraduate	-	-	-		
	Gender Discrimination	Primary school	-	-	-	0,168	0,918
		Middle School	61	3,7158	0,49380		
		High school	199	3,7102	0,52040		
		Associate Degree	39	3,7607	0,52953		
		Bachelor's	31	3,7634	0,64517		
	Organizational Conditions	Primary school	-	-	-	1,377	0,250
		Middle School	61	3,6475	0,60789		
		High school	199	3,6080	0,74341		
Associate Degree		39	3,3974	0,60892			
Bachelor's		31	3,5985	0,67918			

Source: own elaboration.

It is observed that there is no significant difference between the scores of the participants in the sub-dimensions of 'lack of support resources', 'lack of mentors', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' of the scale of difficulties encountered in business life and the situations they have to struggle with and the variable of educational status (Sig. =0.093, Sig.=0.813, Sig.=0.918, and Sig.=0.250). Consequently;

H1c: 'There is a significant difference between the

education levels of female cooks and the lack of support resources.

H1g: 'There is a significant difference between the education levels of female cooks and the lack of mentors.'

H1j: 'There is a significant difference between the education levels of female cooks and gender discrimination.'

H1n: 'The hypotheses "There is a significant difference between the educational status of female cooks and organizational conditions" were rejected.

Table 6. ANOVA test results of the sub-dimensions of 'lack of support resources', 'mentor deficiency', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' of the scale of difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to struggle according to the participants' income status.

	Dimensions	Income status	n	X	s.s.	F value	P value
Scale of difficulties encountered in business life and situations that have to be struggled	Lack of Support Resources	2001-3000 TL	159	3,5325	0,62318	1,267	0,283
		3001-4000 TL	154	3,6385	0,65118		
		4001 TL and more	17	3,4902	0,60228		
	Lack of Mentor	2001-3000 TL	159	3,5031	0,62402	1,330	0,266
		3001-4000 TL	154	3,5996	0,70312		
		4001 TL and more	17	3,9725	0,97098		
	Gender Discrimination	2001-3000 TL	159	3,7212	0,55736	0,047	0,954
		3001-4000 TL	154	3,7273	0,49170		
		4001 TL and more	17	3,6863	0,58298		
	Organizational Conditions	2001-3000 TL	159	3,5692	0,66912	0,268	0,765
		3001-4000 TL	154	3,6266	0,71529		
		4001 TL and more	17	3,6176	0,87553		

Source: own elaboration.

In table 6, it is observed that there is no significant difference between the scores of the participants in the sub-dimensions of 'lack of support resources', 'lack of mentors', 'gender discrimination' and 'organizational conditions' of the scale of difficulties encountered in business life and the situations they have to struggle with, and the variable of income status (Sig. =0.283, Sig.=0.266, Sig.=0.954, and Sig.=0.765. Consequently;

H1d: 'There is a significant difference between the income levels of female cooks and the lack of support resources.'

H1h: 'There is a significant difference between the income levels of female cooks and the lack of mentors.'

H1k: 'There is a significant difference between the income levels of female cooks and gender discrimination.'

H1o: 'There is a significant difference between the income levels of female cooks and organizational conditions.' hypothesis was rejected.

4.2 Qualitative Research Findings

4.2.1 Findings Regarding the Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Interviews were held with 32 female chefs who have achieved success in the sector. The age range of the participants varies between 21 and 50. Working time in the profession of female chefs who work intensively in hotel and restaurant kitchens is between 4 and 28 years. The places of birth of the interviewees were determined as İstanbul, İzmir, Mardin, Aydın, Ankara, İzmit, Edirne, Sivas, Adana, Çanakkale, Safranbolu, Erzincan, Eskişehir, Diyarbakır, Malatya, Çankırı, Muğla, Hatay, Trabzon, Sakarya, Yozgat, respectively.

4.2.2 Themes and Categories Resulting from the Analysis of the Data

In determining the gender barriers faced by female cooks employed in professional kitchens, 7 themes were determined according to the data obtained from the opinions of female cooks. These themes are; role model theme, female chefs' feeling of belonging to the kitchen theme, the effect of the kitchen on the burnout level of female chefs, gender and behavior theme, gender and communication theme, the effect of gender on the kitchen hierarchy and experiential gains from the kitchen.

4.2.1.1 Role Model Theme

In the study, questions were asked to determine the role models that contributed to the female cooks choosing the kitchen department as their working area. Role models are an important approach for female chefs to develop their personal learning and careers. It was aimed to determine the first acquaintance of the participants with the kitchen, who supported the development of their competence in the kitchen and from whom they learned how to cook. The reason for this is the determination of gender stereotypes underlying the culinary culture.

The female chefs participating in the interview have a

female role model. These female role models include mother, older sister, grandmother and mother-in-law. The fact that female chefs are role models that help them get acquainted with the kitchen and contribute to the development of their culinary skills contributes to their inclusion in the kitchen department.

4.2.1.2 Female Chefs' Feeling of Belonging to the Kitchen Theme

In the study, questions were asked to determine the sense of belonging of female cooks to professional kitchens. The sense of belonging to the kitchen helps female cooks to establish a strong relationship between themselves and their work environment.

The strong bond between them not only determines the performance of individuals in the business environment, but also contributes to their peaceful working. From this point of view, it was aimed to determine the sense of belonging by determining the reasons that lead the participants to work in professional kitchens and make them bond, the pleasure they get from the kitchen and the culinary experiences they enjoy the most.

Although the female chefs who participated in the interview mentioned the difficulties of working in the kitchen department, they stated that they enjoyed the opportunities and pace of professional kitchens. All of the female cooks stated that they had difficulties while working in the kitchen, missed the meal times, and continued to work even if they were sick. The female chefs who participated in the interview stated that working in the professional kitchen made them feel peaceful and happy, and they felt that they belonged to the kitchen department with the professional experience they gained during the working period.

4.2.1.3 The Effect of the Kitchen on the Burnout Level of Female Chefs Theme

In the study, questions were asked to determine the burnout levels of female cooks in the kitchen sector and to determine its effect on cooling from the profession. The kitchen department's long and uncertain working hours and difficulties such as workload may cause individuals to be alienated from their profession, to decrease the value they attach to their work, to decrease their performance in the workplace and to quit the job.

For this reason, it was asked to determine the experiences that caused the participants to react sadly and emotionally while working in the kitchen section, the pressure they were exposed to and situations such as condemnation. The female cooks participating in the interview encounter many negative situations while working in the kitchen. These include sexual harassment, physical assault, slang insults and mobbing. These situations may cause female cooks to become alienated from their profession and decrease their performance, and some of them have to receive psychological support in order to continue their daily lives.

4.2.1.4 Gender and Behavior Theme

In the study, questions were asked to female cooks to

determine the effect of being a woman in the kitchen sector on their behaviors and the behaviors exhibited to them. Behaviors caused by gender discrimination have a negative impact on women in working life. It can lead to a decrease in their job performance and to exhibit quitting behavior.

Female cooks who participated in the interview stated that they were discriminated against because of their gender. The participants stated that they are not wanted in the kitchen sector because of their gender, male chefs or their male superiors do not want female chefs in the workplace in order to work comfortably, they are not hired because they are women at the time of recruitment, and especially married women or women with children are eliminated at the time of employment.

4.2.1.5 Gender and Communication Theme

In the study, questions were asked to female cooks to determine whether gender had an effect on communication in professional kitchens. Male dominance is a type of violence that negatively affects women with the help of communication channels. Male domination, which is one of the cornerstones of gender discrimination, can occur not only physically but also verbally. The fact that the kitchen department is dominated by men can shape the communication between men and women.

The female cooks who participated in the interview stated that the communication in the kitchen varies according to the gender of the individuals. They stated that male cooks working in professional kitchens prefer slang and vulgar language among themselves, and generally behave distantly and politely towards women.

Male cooks underestimate them and want to establish authority during communication with female cooks. This situation causes female cooks to change their identities and exhibit masculine behaviors in the workplace. The inability of the women working in the kitchen department to act like themselves leads them to identity confusion.

4.2.1.6 The Effect of Gender on Culinary Hierarchy Theme

In the study, questions were asked to female cooks to determine the effect of gender on the kitchen hierarchy. It was desired to determine the authority and management styles of the participants, the way they control the working environment, and the type of communication they established with their subordinates and superiors. In general, in the hierarchical structure of society, women are more disadvantaged than men in terms of social and economic rights. The hierarchy in the kitchen area varies according to gender and worker rights.

The female cooks who participated in the interview stated that they are democratic and treat their employees equally while managing the kitchen. They stated that they checked the compliance of the working area with the hygiene rules before and after the work in order not to interrupt the work in the kitchen.

4.2.1.7 Experiential Gains from the Kitchen Theme

In the study, questions were asked to female cooks to

determine their experiential gains while working in professional kitchens. Experiential learning is the transformation that female cooks provide with their experiences. Based on the first culinary experiences of the participants, it was desired to determine the transformation brought about by the experiences they gained from the kitchen.

Most of the female cooks who participated in the interview stated that they encountered a lack of self-confidence in their first kitchen experiment, but they overcame this with their experiences from the kitchen. The participants stated that they felt mentally stronger than in the past, but these experiences made them feel tougher.

5 DISCUSSION

Success lies in survival through differentiation that can facilitate a competitive asset. One such competitive asset is the delivery of superior service quality (Kamat, Bhaskaran Pillai, Jan Pech, D'Mello and Chen Chang, 2017, p. 39). In this study, it is aimed to determine the gender barriers that female chefs working in the kitchen departments of 5-star hotels in Antalya encounter in their business life, the factors that prevent them from progressing in their careers, and the situations they have to struggle with. Looking at the positions of female chefs in the kitchen, it was determined that they worked as busboy, demi, pastry chef, cold chef, hot chef, breakfast chef, à la carte chef, assistant chef, banquet chef, butcher chef and chef.

It has been determined that more than half of the female cooks participating in the study are in the position of busboy, which is the lower level in the kitchen hierarchy. Harris and Giuffre (2010: 31) stated in industry reports that women find less space in hotel kitchens than men in higher positions as head chef or section chief. In the study of Everyone and Redden (2017: 130), it was stated that female cooks work as pastry chefs, bakers, chocolatiers and sugar dough masters in the pastry sector, which is seen as feminine in the kitchen.

It was determined that there was no significant difference between the scores obtained from the sub-dimensions of the scale of the difficulties encountered in business life and the situations that had to be struggled, and the variables of age, marital status, income level and educational status. Accordingly, it can be said that the socio-demographic characteristics of female cooks determined in the study do not have an effect on the lack of support resources, lack of mentors, gender discrimination and organizational conditions that they encounter and have to struggle with in the working environment.

Gupta, Kanu and Lamsal (2021 p. 61) obtained the opposite result in their study and found that the gender discrimination faced by women differs according to gender, age, educational status and economic status. Raza and Murad (2010, p.541) stated that socio-demographic characteristics such as age and gender and the cultural structure of the environment are effective on the inequality that women experience due to their gender in their study to determine the relationship between gender inequality in Pakistan and socio-demographic characteristics. has done.

Chandrashekarappa, Kadiyala, and Nagendra (2018, p. 239) examined the gender discrimination faced by young women and their relationship with their familial and socio-demographic characteristics, and found that the gender discrimination that young women are exposed to varies according to their age, marital status, place of residence, education level and education level of their parents.

According to the results obtained from the qualitative part of the research, the role models of female cooks were determined as mother, older sister, grandmother and mother-in-law. Role models are an important concept in explaining the impact of individuals on decision-making processes in working life (Gretzel and Bowser, 2013, p.176).

Haddaji, Garrigós and Segovia (2017, p.324) stated that it is difficult for female chefs to access role models that help them develop their careers professionally. The fact that most of the female cooks participating in the study chose their role models from the female figures in the family in the home environment rather than the professional kitchen environment supports this situation. Cano (2019, p. 54), who achieved a similar result, determined in his study that women are seen as a strong role model in the field of kitchen, but they are left behind in the field of employment in professional kitchens.

The female cooks participating in the study have to face many difficulties and work more diligently while working in professional kitchens. Harris and Giuffre (2010: 27) stated that female chefs should work more than other sectors and love the culinary profession in order to have a place in professional kitchens. Agmapisarn (2016: 31), who achieved a similar result, stated in her study that female chefs should work harder than men in order to have a place in the kitchen unit, they should have more passion and motivation, so that they can feel themselves belong to the kitchen. In the study, female chefs stated that they enjoyed the opportunities for self-development and creativity offered by professional kitchens, and that they found the kitchen to be brisk.

Female chefs who are happy to work in the kitchen department feel that they belong to the kitchen thanks to the professional experience they have gained over time. The sense of belonging to the kitchen is also important in terms of helping female chefs establish a strong relationship between themselves and their work environment. In support of this view, Hansford (2011: 69) stated that despite the difficulties that cooks have faced throughout their careers, they look at these difficulties with pride and these difficulties push them to think that they are a special person to be successful in the kitchen industry.

In the study, the difficulties faced by female cooks while working in professional kitchens and many factors that cause emotional reactions were determined. These include sexual harassment, physical assault, slang insults and mobbing. After these experiences, there were also female cooks who had to receive psychological treatment in order to continue their daily lives. Bartholomew (1996: 210) obtained a similar result in his study and found that female cooks had to make more efforts to prove themselves in the kitchen section, and that they were harassed and bullied at different levels during this process.

Pritchard (2014: 320) defines different levels of harassment as touching, verbal abuse, inappropriate display, sexual jokes and touching. Parent-Thirion, Macias, Hurley, and Vermeyley (2007: 37) found in their study that young women

(under 30 years old) working in the hotel and restaurant industries are more exposed to harassment and bullying than other industries. Burrow and Yakinthou (2015: 675) stated in their study that the hegemonic masculinity ideology of professional kitchens leads to bullying, violence and aggression in the working environment.

Hsu, Liu, and Tsaur (2019: 1702) stated in their study that bullying, violence and mobbing in the workplace negatively affect the well-being of employees. These experiences that female chefs encounter while working in professional kitchens may cause them to be alienated from the culinary profession, and to decrease the performance and value they give to the job.

It has been determined that female cooks working in professional kitchens are discriminated against because of their gender. The participants stated that they are not wanted in the kitchen department because they are women, and that male cooks or their superiors do not want them in the workplace in order to behave more comfortably. They also stated that they were not accepted during the recruitment process because of their gender, and especially female cooks who were married or had children were eliminated during the interview. In support of this finding, Min (2019: 19) found in his study that the desire of female chefs to have children causes the thought that they cannot fulfill the conditions necessary for promotion in the kitchen department, and that female chefs must choose between family and a successful career today.

Li and Leung (2001: 194), in their research in hotel businesses, revealed that women managers face many difficulties if they cannot get enough support from their families. FungaiZengeni, Tendani and Zengeni (2014: 9) stated in their study that male chefs do not like being managed by female chefs and therefore they do not want women to rise in the kitchen. In their study, Campos-Soria, Marchante-Mera and Roperto-Garcia (2011: 101) examined gender discrimination and found that there is occupational segregation in the hotel industry, women are employed in low-responsibility jobs and men are employed in high-responsibility jobs. In the study of Ng and Pine (2003: 85) on the distribution of the gender of managers in accommodation businesses in Hong Kong by departments, they found that general managers are mostly men.

It has been determined that women mostly undertake managerial duties in housekeeping and front office. Campos-Soria, Ortega-Aruaza and Roperto-Garcia (2009: 863) stated that women's working conditions and wages are worse than men's. Behaviors caused by gender discrimination have a negative impact on women in working life. It can lead to a decrease in job performance and to exhibit quitting behavior.

It has been determined that the communication established by female cooks in the kitchen unit varies according to the gender of their colleagues. While working in the kitchen, female cooks are cautious not to be harassed or misunderstood by men. Being a female cook in the kitchen affects their communication with their teammates and causes them to exhibit masculine behaviors. In addition, women experience identity confusion as they cannot act as themselves in professional kitchens.

Burrow and Yakinthou (2015: 675) concluded that women working in professional kitchens exhibit masculine

behaviors and have to assume a masculine identity. He also stated in his study that individuals who have difficulty in displaying masculine behavior are excluded from the culinary profession. Female cooks participating in the study stated that male cooks use slang and vulgar communication language with their fellows in the kitchen unit.

Wynn and Correll (2018:161-162) found that male individuals exhibit masculine behaviors in the working environment, speak harshly and slang, and are more sensitive when there are women around, and cannot exhibit their male-male behavior. In support of this data, Pöllänen (2021: 1) concluded that men use a harsh and aggressive language among themselves and cannot exhibit these behaviors in the presence of women.

Male cooks underestimate them and want to establish authority during communication with female cooks. Furumo and Pearson (2007: 47) found in their study that men communicate to establish dominance and authority, while women use communication to establish relationships and gain trust. In the study, some of the female cooks are jealous of their fellows in the kitchen and work after each other, while the other part establishes a sincere and level communication and good friendships with their fellows.

Anderson and Martin (1995: 245) found in their study that women have a compassionate and comfortable communication style with a task motive in the organization. Robinson, Solnet and Breakey (2014: 72) stated that female chefs are more compassionate and less aggressive in the kitchen than men. Meloury and Signal (2014) concluded that chefs working in higher positions such as head chef or assistant chef in professional kitchens are more aggressive towards their lower ranks.

It has been determined that the female cooks participating in the interview are democratic and treat their employees equally while managing the kitchen. They stated that they manage their employees by organizing them according to the work plan and that they correctly determine the task sharing of their employees in managing the kitchen area. Haddaji (2018: 162) found that female supervisors work more regularly and team-oriented, and they consider it important to deal with subordinates and give clear instructions. In his study, Cano (2019: 54-55) concluded that female chefs have a supportive, caring, helpful, hospitable and understanding character as a team member.

Haddaji, Albors-Garrigósa and García-Segovia (2017: 53) found in their study that female chefs pay more attention to the professional and personal attitudes of their teammates in the kitchen. The female cooks who participated in the study stated that they acted equally and respectfully when communicating with their subordinates in the kitchen and that they communicated without damaging the self-confidence of their employees.

Most of the female cooks who participated in the interview experienced insecurity in their first kitchen experiment, but they overcame this situation with their experiences from the kitchen. Randhawa (2004: 337-338) stated that self-confidence has positive effects on performance. The experiences of female chefs from the kitchen strengthen them mentally and physically, enabling them to persevere and to persevere more difficult than in their previous lives. These experiences cause them to adopt a

tougher temperament and to trust people less than before. In addition, these gains help them achieve success and grow in their business.

As a result; Women are an important role model for the professional kitchen. However, it is thought that female chefs who choose their role models from female figures in the home environment while working in the sector are difficult to access role models in the professional kitchen. While working in professional kitchens, female chefs face many challenges such as sexual harassment, physical assault, slang insults and mobbing.

However, they are happy to enjoy the opportunities for self-development and creativity that the kitchen offers them, and to find the tempo in the kitchen entertaining. The majority of the participants, who stated that the gender barriers they encountered while working in the kitchen unit decreased with the increase in the employment of female cooks and mechanization, stated that they were against gender discrimination. They stated that they are equal and fair in their kitchens and that they do not allow gender discrimination to occur. The female chefs, who draw a reliable and self-sacrificing image in the kitchen, stated that they work in the sector in a disciplined, hard-working manner and without hesitation from competition.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The aim of this study was to determine the gender barriers faced by female chefs working in the kitchen departments of five-star hotels in Antalya, the factors that prevent them from progressing in their careers, and the situations they have to struggle with. In addition, it was aimed to determine the perception of gender in hotel kitchens based on the experiences of successful and well-known female chefs in professional kitchens.

According to the opinion expressed by the participants, female chefs are not wanted in the kitchen department because of their gender, and male chefs or their superiors do not want female chefs in the workplace in order to work comfortably. Participants stated that they were not hired at the time of job application because they were women, and especially women who were married or had children were eliminated at the time of employment.

In the kitchen, female chefs stated that men choose a comfortable, slang and harsh way of communication with their fellows and that they cannot exhibit these behaviors in the presence of female cooks. The masculine nature of the professional kitchen can be seen as a reason for male cooks to prefer their same gender as workmates.

Female cooks stated that they acted cautiously while working in the kitchen department in order not to be harassed or misunderstood by men. She stated that being a woman working in the kitchen unit affected their communication, that she had to exhibit masculine behaviors in order to get along with her teammates, that she could not act like herself, and that they had identity confusion in the working environment.

As a result; Despite the prepared state policies, the discrimination against the biological differences of the individuals continues in the individuals raised by the society. When examined in the historical process, it is seen that the prejudices of the society against working women continue.

The statements made by female chefs in the study show that gender barriers continue in professional kitchens today. While working in the kitchen department, many difficulties are encountered, both physical and psychological. In this direction, the following suggestions can be offered to eliminate the gender barriers that female cooks face in professional kitchens.

6.1 Recommendations for the industry

Gender barriers are not just situations faced by women working in professional kitchens. Since it is a problem for the society in general and for women working in many business lines, it should be tackled.

In order to prevent the problems caused by women working in double shifts in both the home and kitchen departments, information programs should be organized through the written and visual media.

In order to prevent the harassment faced by individuals working in the tourism sector, seminars for women and men should be given in businesses within the sector.

Regardless of their gender, women working in professional kitchens should be treated equally and fairly in the distribution and distribution of duties within the sector.

Some of the women in some businesses cannot make their voices heard against the violence and bullying they face. In order to prevent this, a platform should be created where women can access and make their voices heard.

By creating platforms where the success stories of female chefs who have achieved success in professional kitchens are shared, the empowering effect of solidarity should be realized.

6.2 Suggestions for future academic studies

Only the opinions of female chefs were included in the study. Comparisons can be made by including male chefs in the study. In order to better understand the gender barriers that female chefs face in professional kitchens, a comparison can be made by discussing the study with chefs from different countries.

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Final Table. CRediT author statement.

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims		x
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models		x
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components		
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs		x
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data		x
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	x	
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	x	
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse		x
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	x	
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages		x
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation		x
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team		x
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution		x
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication		x

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